

Possibilities of using inclusive growth in ensuring sustainable development in the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: In this article, the conditions of sustainable development, the description of "inclusiveness" and "inclusive growth" by the producers and the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the possibilities of inclusive growth in ensuring sustainable development in Uzbekistan are analyzed, and relevant comments are made.

Keywords: Sustainable development, sustainability, inclusiveness, inclusive growth, Human Development Index (HDI), education, poverty reduction, and employment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasining ishlab chiqaruvchilari va hukumat tomonidan barqaror rivojlanish shartlari, "inklyuzivlik" va "inklyuziv o'sish" tavsifi, hamda O'zbekistonda barqaror rivojlanishni ta'minlashda inklyuziv o'sish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinib, tegishli fikr-mulohazalar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Barqaror rivojlanish, barqarorlik, "inklyuzivlik", "inklyuziv o'sish", Inson taraqqiyot indeksi (HDI), ta'lim, kambag'allikni qisqartirish, va bandlikni ta'minlash.

Introduction.

Aiming to reduce risks in the development of each country, anticipate unexpected external effects, improve the well-being of the population and raise the standards of its living conditions, countries, of course, in order to avoid sudden and unexpected fluctuations in the structure of the economy, ensure stability and thereby promote development. In this regard, achieving inclusive growth is a necessary conditionality. In particular, Uzbekistan is making a number of efforts to achieve inclusive growth.

The main part.

Requirements of sustainable development. The sustainable development of the country largely depends on internal and external cooperation. Economic development plays an important role in achieving sustainable development, and

Uzbekistan has successfully halved the country's poverty level in this area since 2017.

Sustainable development is a process of economic and social changes, the purpose of which is, of course, to ensure the quality of life of people. Depending on the aspects we look at and the goals we set, we can set different conditions for sustainable development by the state. These conditions provide for the achievement of the intended goals and establish the limits of the state's economic and social policy. Generally speaking, the conditions of sustainable development imply the prevention of sudden and unexpected fluctuations by establishing stability or stability in development. In particular and in a broader view, it is observed that the limits are set in relation to the following with the participation of manufacturers and the government¹:

- Conditions for implementation of structural changes: Basically, for countries whose economy is based on science or clearly defined.
- Conditions for modernization and diversification of the economy: For the industrializing countries and beyond.
- Conditions for combating inflation: For almost all countries, regardless of type.
- Monetary and Fiscal conditions: For countries with stimulus or restrictive policies.
- Investment operating conditions: For almost all countries.

Definition of "inclusiveness" and "inclusive growth". "Inclusiveness" should mean "covering". Inclusive growth is economic growth that raises the standard of living for a broad swath of the population.²

Sustainable economic growth requires inclusive growth. This is sometimes difficult to maintain because economic growth can create negative externalities such as increased corruption, which is a major problem in developing countries. Nevertheless, an emphasis on inclusion, especially in terms of equality of opportunity in terms of access to markets, resources and a fair regulatory environment, is a critical component of successful growth. An inclusive growth

¹ Consumers are affected by the actions and decisions of governments and producers in providing the conditions imposed on these factors. If consumers' incomes increase their purchasing power, they become an asset in the process of sustainable development.

² Cerra, Valerie (2021), "[An Inclusive Growth Framework](#)", How to Achieve Inclusive Growth, Oxford University Press, pp. 131, doi:[10.1093/oso/9780192846938.003.0001](#), ISBN [978-0-19-284693-8](#)

approach takes a long-term perspective as it focuses on productive employment as a means of raising the incomes and living standards of the poor and marginalized groups.

It is widely recognized that inclusive growth is almost impossible to achieve in the real world. On the one hand, there is a lack of a comprehensive and globally recognized set of standards for systematically measuring the inclusiveness of growth, which makes data collection and policy evaluation difficult. Both its intangibility and long-term perspective make it less desirable for policymakers than other more visible economic goals. On the other hand, as some critics point out, the many negative externalities of growth are fundamentally at odds with the goal of inclusiveness, which further complicates the situation. In many real-life situations, inclusion is given less consideration than economic growth and is sometimes sacrificed altogether.

Opportunities for inclusive growth in sustainable development in Uzbekistan.

Since there is no single model for promoting inclusive growth in the world, it is more appropriate to use the "Human Development Index" to highlight the possibilities of using inclusive growth to ensure sustainable development in Uzbekistan. In the latest Human Development Index (HDI) report prepared by the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), Uzbekistan ranked 106th among 193 countries and regions of the world. The data covers the year 2022, which indicates a decrease of one position compared to the previous year's ranking. Countries were assessed on three key indicators of human development – life expectancy at birth, average years of schooling and gross national income per capita. The average life expectancy in Uzbekistan is 71.7 years, the education period is 12 years, and the gross income per capita is 8056 dollars. With a score of 0.727 on the Human Development Index in 2022, Uzbekistan maintains its status in the high human index category and is located between Egypt and Vietnam. Other countries in the Central Asian region, specifically Kazakhstan was in 67th place, Turkmenistan in 94th, Kyrgyzstan in 117th, Tajikistan in 126th place, the first place according to the index is Switzerland with 0.967 points, the third places belonged to Norway and Iceland. Hong Kong and Denmark also made the top five.

Corruption is considered one of the main indicators that is formed as a negative effect of the country's economic growth and is an obstacle to ensuring inclusive growth. According to the Transparency website, Uzbekistan was ranked 121 out of

180 countries by the level of corruption in 2023 and has a score of 33 out of 100³. This limits the country's ability to achieve a certain level of inclusive growth.

According to the Doing Business rating, Uzbekistan received 69 points.⁴ In this case, the business environment is evaluated based on 100 and indicates the average indicator for our country.

In general, inclusive growth is manifested in improving the living conditions of the poor. Because of this, the middle and upper classes are actively active, using the existing capital and conditions optimally to improve their living conditions. Determining the level of population income is considered as the first step towards inclusive growth. The reason is that the rich and poor strata of the population are identified and divided into the appropriate categories.

Uzbekistan is also making efforts towards inclusive growth in ensuring sustainable development. Programs to increase human capital and social inclusion are being implemented in Uzbekistan, which aims not to leave anyone behind.

Inclusiveness in education: Notably, pre-primary education coverage has increased from 21 percent in 2015 to 70 percent in 2022. Likewise, higher education enrollment rates rose from 8 percent to 38 percent, with targeted efforts to support women's entry.

Poverty reduction: The country has set ambitious goals, including a plan to halve poverty by 2026 and further reduce it to 5 percent by 2030.

Ensuring employment: There is also a focus on reducing youth unemployment and providing employment to an additional 1 million youth by 2030.

Infrastructure development: Another important aspect of Uzbekistan's strategy. The plans include providing clean drinking water to all settlements, increasing electrified railways, and investing heavily in road construction and reconstruction.

Profitability: "Strategy for the development of New Uzbekistan in 2022-2026" aims to raise Uzbekistan to a country with an above-average income by 2030. It focuses on specific, measurable goals, including reducing poverty and improving access to education. The strategy also aims to improve governance and inclusive institutions, fight corruption, promote civil society and decentralization, support rural development and ensure sustainable development in vulnerable areas.

Environmental sustainability and energy: Recognizing the importance of environmental sustainability, Uzbekistan has developed a strategy to transition to a "green" economy by 2030. This strategy includes increasing the share of renewable

³ [//www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023](https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023)

⁴ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/IC.BUS.EASE.XQ>

energy sources in total electricity generation to 25 percent by 2026 and doubling energy efficiency. In this regard, the strategy for the transition to a green economy until 2030 envisages increasing the share of renewable energy sources in total electricity production to 25% by 2026, doubling energy efficiency, and halving the energy capacity of the gross domestic product. . In Uzbekistan, it is planned to launch renewable energy sources (RES) in order to increase the share of renewable energy sources in the country's total electricity production to 30 percent.

Conclusion.

As Uzbekistan continues on the path of sustainable development, it will develop comprehensive strategies to improve population welfare, reduce poverty, ensure inclusive employment, prevent corruption, improve education, income levels, and life expectancy. The country is moving towards inclusive growth, implying the improvement of indicators such as sustainability for the lower strata of the population.

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